

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

FEATURES OF PLUTO'S ROTATION AROUND ITS AXIS AND AROUND THE SUN

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ABSTRACT

Pluto's orbit differs significantly from the orbits of the large planets of the Solar System. After all, if they are almost circular and close to the plane of the ecliptic, then Pluto's orbit is inclined to the ecliptic by more than 17° , and with an eccentricity value of 0.249 it is significantly elongated. Therefore, the average distance between Pluto and the Sun varies from 39.53 AU at perihelion to almost 49.31 AU at aphelion. This leads to the fact that the intensity of illumination from the Sun changes on the surface by a factor of 2.8. Pluto's rotation period around the Sun is almost 248 years. Due to the elongated orbit, Pluto periodically approaches Neptune. On September 5, 1989, it last passed the perihelion point. And at this moment, from 02/07/1979 to 02/11/1999, for more than 20 years, Pluto was closer to the Sun than Neptune. Before that, the same situation occurred for 14 years, from 07/11/1735 to 09/15/1749. However, due to the large inclination of Pluto's orbit to the plane of the ecliptic, it does not intersect with Neptune's orbit, since passing the perihelion point, Pluto is at a distance of 10 AU above the plane of the ecliptic. For this reason, Pluto cannot approach the planet Neptune closer than 17 AU. But Pluto can sometimes approach Uranus by almost 11 AU. Such an orbital resonance between Neptune and Pluto is very stable and persists for millions of years. And since the argument of Pluto's perihelion is close to 90° , this value provides a significant distance both to the ecliptic plane and to the nearby giant planets when passing through the perihelion point. Such characteristics allow Pluto to avoid approaching Neptune. The period of rotation of Pluto around its own axis is 6.387 Earth days. The same value is equal to the period of rotation of Charon around Pluto and around its axis. Therefore, Pluto and Charon always face each other with the same side. They are the largest bodies in the Solar System with mutual synchronous rotation. The Pluto-Charon system of bodies is distinguished by the fact that due to the large mass of the satellite Charon; their center of mass is located outside the limits for both bodies. Therefore, they are sometimes called a double planet. The last equinox for Pluto took place on 16.12.1987.

Keywords: Pluto, dwarf planet, orbital features, double planet, synchronous rotation.

It is known that the orbits of the large planets [12-14, 25-29] of the Solar System (except Mercury) are almost circular and close to the ecliptic plane. And as follows from the data in Table 1, the orbit of the dwarf

planet [9, 15, 23] Pluto (Fig. 1) differs significantly from them.

Fig. 1. Mosaic of images of Pluto taken by the New Horizons space probe on July 14, 2015, from a distance of 450,000 km (https://pluto.jhuapl.edu/Galleries/Featured-Images/pics/BIG_P_COLOR_2_TRUE_COLOR1.png).

Table 1.

Main characteristics of Pluto and its orbit.

Orbital characteristics	
Semi-major axis	5906.38 million km 39.482 AU
Perihelion	4436.82 million km 29.658 AU
Aphelion	7375.93 million km 49.305 AU
Eccentricity	0.249
Orbital period	247.94 Earth years
Orbital period	14179 Pluto solar days
Mean orbital velocity	4.67 km/s
Mean anomaly	14.86°
Orbital inclination to the ecliptic	17.14°
Orbital inclination to the Sun's equator	11.88°
Longitude of ascending node	110.303°
Longitude of pericenter	224.067°
Time of last pericenter	5 September 1989
Pericenter argument	113.763°
Physical characteristics	
Average radius	1187±4 km
Oblateness	<1 %
Surface area	17.7 million km ²
Mass	(1.303 ± 0.003) × 10 ²² kg 0.0022 of the Earth's mass
Average density	1.860 ± 0.013 g/sm ³
Surface acceleration due to gravity	0.617 m/s ² (0.063 g)
Second cosmic velocity	1.210 km/s
Rotation period	-6.387 s
Equatorial rotational velocity	13.5 m/s
Axis inclination to orbit	122.53°
Right elevation of the north pole	132.99°
North pole inclination	-6.16°
Bond albedo	0.4-0.6
Geometric albedo	0.5-0.7
Surface temperature	33-55 K
Apparent magnitude	>13.65 (average 15.1)
Apparent angular size	0.06-0.11"
Axis inclination to orbit	122.53°
Atmosphere	
Surface pressure	1 Pa (as of 2015)
Altitude scale	about 60 km
Composition	nitrogen with admixtures of methane and carbon monoxide

It turned out to be more than 17° inclined to the ecliptic and significantly elongated. The average distance between Pluto and the Sun is 39.53 AU (5.913 billion km). But due to the large value of the eccentricity of the orbit (0.249), the distance to the Sun varies from 29.66 AU at perihelion to almost 49.31 AU at aphelion (4.437-7.376 billion km). The intensity of illumination differs by a factor of 2.8. This leads to a change in the temperature on its surface from 33K to almost 60K [22, 24]. The period of Pluto's rotation around the Sun is about 248 years.

It last passed the place of perihelion on September 5, 1989, and at this time it began to move away from the Sun [6]. Pluto's motion along its orbit is quite chaotic and is described by highly nonlinear equations. Therefore, it can only be predicted a few million years back or forward. And this can be noticed only after fairly long observations of it. The typical time for the

development of such changes for Pluto is about 10-20 million years [6].

If observations are made over shorter periods of time, its movements will seem to be almost regularly periodic along an elliptical orbit. Although in reality, Pluto's orbit shifts slightly with each revolution, and over time it changes significantly from the initial movements.

Therefore, predicting Pluto's movements for more distant moments in time is quite difficult [10, 32]. Pluto is in a 3:2 orbital resonance with the giant planet [7, 13, 20] Neptune. That is, Pluto periodically approaches Neptune [30]. In each such cycle, when Pluto passes through perihelion, Neptune is 50° behind Pluto; and when Pluto passes perihelion a second time, Neptune will have already made one and a half revolutions around the Sun and will be at about the same distance, but already in front of Pluto. And when Neptune and Pluto will be on the same line with the Sun and on the

same side of it, Pluto will be at aphelion. Thus, for part of its orbit, Pluto is even closer to the Sun [18, 22-24] than Neptune (Fig. 2). The last time this happened was from 02/07/1979 to 02/11/1999. Calculations have shown that before that, Pluto occupied the same position for 14 years from 07/11/1735 to 09/15/1749.

Due to the rather large inclination of Pluto's orbit to the plane of the ecliptic, it does not intersect with the

orbit of Neptune. After all, passing the perihelion point, Pluto is at a distance of 10 AU above the plane of the ecliptic. For this reason, Pluto cannot approach the planet Neptune closer than 17 AU. But Pluto can approach Uranus by almost 11 AU [10, 32].

Fig. 2. The scheme of the intersection of the orbits of Pluto and Neptune (https://static.wixstatic.com/media/195ad9_30ec8c1b35374b28999628e7d7f4f8bd~mv2.png).

Such an orbital resonance between Neptune and Pluto is very stable and persists for millions of years [30, 31]. It is believed that Pluto acquired a resonance with Neptune over billions of years of numerous approaches, and this changed its orbit. However, it turned out that in addition to the 3:2 orbital resonance, several other resonances and influences [11, 17, 19, 21] are of great importance, which are also reflected in certain features of their relative motion and additionally stabilize the features of Pluto's orbit.

The argument of the perihelion of Pluto is close to 90° [31]. It is this value that provides a significant distance both to the plane of the ecliptic and to the nearby giant planets during the passage of perihelion. All this together allows avoiding the rapprochement of Pluto with Neptune. This is a direct consequence of the so-

called Kozai effect [30], which compares the values of the eccentricity and inclination of Pluto's orbit relative to a more massive body, which, in this case, is Neptune. The moments when the angular difference between the inclination of Pluto's perihelion and Neptune's orbit is the smallest occur approximately every 10,000 years [1]. The longitudes of the ascending nodes for the orbits of these two planetary bodies (i.e., the points at which they cross the ecliptic plane) are in resonance with the aforementioned oscillations. If these two longitudes coincide, then the perihelion point of Pluto's orbit will make an angle of 90° with the ecliptic (Fig. 3). At such moments, Pluto will be in a 1:1 super resonance above the plane of Neptune's orbit and will be furthest away from it [30]. The full cycle is completed in approximately 20,000 years [1, 6].

Fig. 3. Kepler orbital elements relative to the main plane (<https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/0/01/Orbit.svg>).

The period of rotation of Pluto around its own axis is 6.387 Earth days. The same value is equal to the period of rotation of Charon around Pluto and around its axis. For this reason, Pluto and Charon are always turned with the same side to each other. They are the largest bodies in the Solar System with mutual synchronous rotation [3]. This phenomenon was used as a natural point for starting longitudes. That is, the zero meridian on Pluto passes through the center of the hemisphere facing Charon [2, 16].

The system of bodies "Pluto – Charon" [4] is distinguished by the fact that due to the large mass of the satellite Charon, their center of mass is located outside the limits for both bodies. Therefore, they are sometimes called a double planet [8].

Pluto's axis of rotation is oriented relative to the orbital plane in much the same way as Uranus'. Its inclination exceeds 122° . Therefore, Pluto also practically "lies on its side" and rotates around its axis in the opposite direction to most planets. The last equinox for Pluto occurred on December 16, 1987 [5]. And the solstice will occur in the late 2020s [5]. Thus, the equinox on Pluto now almost coincides with the moment of passing the perihelion of the orbit.

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